
Science, Environment, Technology, and Society (SETS) Based Student Worksheet Development to Improve Critical Thinking of Elementary School Students

Susana¹, Distrik, I.W*², Surbakti, A³, Nyeneng, I.D.P⁴

Article history:

Received November, 30 2022, Accepted: February, 02 2022; Displayed Online: February 18, 2022; Published: June 30, 2022

Keywords

*Worksheet,
SETS,
Student's Critical
Thinking Skill;*

Abstract

This study is to produce a valid, practical and effective worksheet for grade IV elementary school students. This study uses 10 steps design developed by Borg and Gall. Content and construct validity tests by experts were done before field testing the worksheet to 58 student samples from Bandar Lampung public elementary school containing 28 students of experiment group and 30 students of control group. Samples were taken by using cluster random sampling. This study used static pretest-posttest study design. The SETS worksheet is: 1) valid by content (77) and by construct (92 for media validity and 83.33 for language validity); 2) practical (89.33% product implementation and 83.29% positive students' responses); 3) effective (n-gains are 0.56 for experiment group and 0.27 for control group). SETS worksheet is valid, practical, and effective to use by grade IV students to improve their critical thinking skills.

¹University of Lampung, Lampung, Indonesia

²University of Lampung, Lampung, Indonesia; Email:wayandistrik8@gmail.com

³University of Lampung, Lampung, Indonesia

⁴University of Lampung, Lampung, Indonesia

1. Introduction

Curriculum 2013 requires educators to train students in elementary and higher educational levels to think critically and creatively. Educators should also integrate technology in learning, so that students are able to use technology properly based on their ages and needs. Having critical thinking skills; that is critical, creative, communicative, and collaborative, is important in 21st century learning. This will equip learners in facing problems in the future; not only in classroom learning (BSNP, 2007). In learning educators must be able to guide students to be involved in learning and able to provide simple and further explanations for a natural event or phenomenon with certain strategies to enable students drawing conclusions. Besides being critical, students are also required to be skilful in thinking creatively, such as abilities to evaluate, to detail, to be flexible, and to be fluent in arguing. In

this learning educators must prepare teaching materials including worksheets. A worksheet must be designed based on students' characteristics, learning materials, and learning objectives.

An observation done to grade IV students in Public Elementary School 1 of Way Halim Housing shows that students have less critical thinking skills. Educators do not have proper strategies to guide students to provide simple explanations for a natural phenomenon or to solve a problem. Students' initial ability test results confirm their less critical thinking skills. 5 students have moderate critical thinking skills while 18 have lower critical thinking skills. 10 students show less problem solving abilities in energy source learning material, 5 students show less problem solving abilities in energy form changes learning material, and 3 students show less problem solving abilities in uses of energy sources learning material. In addition, learners indeed do not show critical thinking skills because they refer their explanations based on answers from books and they do not explain with their own thinking. Student's critical thinking skills are not yet trained by asking questions or explaining. If this condition goes on and on, this would inhibit learning process and learning objectives may not be able to attain.

The use of worksheet in learning can enable learners to learn autonomously, to learn understanding and working a written assignment. The observation result shows that educators do not yet develop worksheets according to learning objectives, and they use worksheets published by a publishers even though these worksheets' contents are less in accordance with learning objectives. Steps presented in these worksheets are less training learners to do scientific process, to analyze, and to find out a concept. Therefore, a development for Science, Environment, Technology, and Society (SETS) based worksheet is required to improve critical thinking skill with learning implementations according to scientific approach as it is required by curriculum 2013. SETS-based worksheet presents structured questions that are able to help learners to understand and memorize more about learning materials and to draw conclusions of what learners have learned, so that students would not find difficulties to have structured questions after having learning. Therefore, SETS-based worksheet learning model would help learners to improve their critical thinking abilities. Learning with SETS-based worksheet principally would guide learners to think and solve everyday problems. This would enable learners to critically investigate scientific problems they find, to learn how scientific knowledge is acquired, to understand scientific knowledge better, and to evaluate scientific knowledge (Autieri et al., 2016).

2. Materials and Methods

This is a research and development (R & D) research similar to what was developed by Borg & Gall. This contains of 10 steps which are grouped into 4 stages; stage 1 introduction, stage 2 planning and development, stage 3 field testing, and stage 4 dissemination. Theoretical studies are done to collect initial information and empirical reviews in introduction stage. It is to collect data by initial study. Planning and development stage is to design a product (the worksheet) according to a model and objective to attain, and then create the product according to the predetermined design. Development would produce an interesting and proper product that is feasible to implement in classrooms. After the product having been tested for its content and construct validities by experts and peer reviews, the product would be field tested in schools in the field testing stage. The product of this study is Science, Environment, Technology, and Society (SETS)-based worksheet that is tested to improve critical thinking abilities of grade IV students in elementary school. The learning theme in this worksheet is Theme 2; Saving Energy – Sub-theme 2; the Energy Use.

The flow chart of the SETS-based worksheet development in this study is based on steps by Borg & Gall, and it can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 1. Steps for research and development
(Development model adaptation (Borg & Gall, 1983; Sugiyono, 2008))

This study was located in Public Elementary School 1 in Way Halim Housing, Lampung province, Indonesia. Population was all 118 grade IV students in Public Elementary School 1 in Way Halim Housing and it can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Study Population

No	Classroom	Learners	Educators
1	Classroom IV A	28	1
2	Classroom IV B	30	1
3	Classroom IV C	30	1
4	Classroom IV D	30	1
	Total	118	4

Samples were taken with purposive sampling. They were classroom IVA as experiment group and classroom IVB as control group. Data were collected by some means: 1) Likert scale validation sheets filled by experts containing of content and construct validation sheets; 2) observation results from learning implementation and students' responses to the product used in learning; and 3) test instrument. Data 1) and 2) were to see SETS-worksheet product practicality in learning and data 3) was to see the product effectiveness in attaining learning objective. Test instrument was tested for its validity and reliability before it was used.

Data validity analysis was done descriptively by grouping data into invalid, less valid, valid enough, valid, and very valid categories. Finally data were categorized into valid and invalid categories. Data analysis on practicality interpreted data into low implementation, moderate implementation, and high implementation categories. Low category had average score less than 60, moderate category was between 61 and 80, and high category was between 81 and 100. Data analysis on effectiveness was done with inferential tests; the normality test, homogeneity test, and independent sample t-test. N-gains of critical thinking abilities between experiment and control groups were analyzed by using SPSS version 23.

3. Results and Discussions

The need analysis result shows that all educators (100%) need worksheets as teaching materials for thematic subjects and all educators agree that worksheets have an important role in learning to deliver materials so that students would be active in learning. Educators use worksheets

in learning even though some of them are less in accordance with characteristics of learners and learning objectives, because the common worksheets are coming from publishers in the market. Educators need worksheets that are most suitable with characteristics of learners and learning materials that are presented in simple language and easy to implement by educators. The product of this study, the SETS-based worksheet, is to improve critical thinking skill. This is a research and development study using 10 steps by Borg and Gall (1983:775). Step 8, 9, and 10 are done after the product is validated theoretically and empirically.

SETS-based Worksheet Validity

SETS-based worksheet validity in improving critical thinking ability is seen from assessment results of three experts; teaching material expert, language expert, and media expert. The validation results can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2. SETS-based worksheet validation test results by experts

No	Test	Expert			Average	Description
		1	2	3		
1	Teaching material validity	77	75	79	77	Valid
2	Construct validity					
	a. Media/figures	92	91	93	92	Valid
	b. Language validity	85	81	84	83.33	Valid

Table 2 shows that teaching material validity score is 77 (valid), language validity score is 83.33 (valid) and media/figure validity score is 92 (very valid). SETS-based worksheet being seen from its content and construct overall is valid and proper to use to improve elementary school student's critical thinking skill in 'the use of energy' teaching material. This worksheet is composed based on SETS model steps and it enables social interaction between teacher and student and creates student's response. Developed material is supported with teaching material that generates student's motivation. SETS-based worksheet is composed in accordance with curriculum 2013 that enables students to do observation, think logically and critically, and be able to solve practical problems in daily life. SETS-based worksheet also meets elements of update, truth, and in accordance with learning objective to attain; the critical thinking ability that includes providing brief and further explanations, using proper strategy, and concluding.

SETS-based worksheet have characteristics that are suggested by Arends (1997). It is 1) theoretically rational – it is composed based on learning theory study such as cognitive and constructivism learning theories; 2) having a clear learning objective – by following SETS steps; 3) easy to implement by educators in classrooms, and 4) requiring classroom structure or learning environment.

SETS-based Worksheet Practicality in Theme 2 'Saving Energy' – Sub-theme 2 'the Use of Energy' Teaching Material for grade IV of Elementary School

SETS-based worksheet practicality in improving critical thinking skill can be seen from tests into small and big groups that are measured with learning implementation indicator by using this worksheet and student's response indicator toward the worksheet in learning. Student's response indicator contains of interesting, readability, and usefulness aspects. SETS-based worksheet implementation in learning contains of initial, main, and closing activities. SETS-based worksheet implementation is presented briefly in Table 3 below.

Table 3. SETS-based worksheet implementation in learning

Observation aspect	Observer		Description
	Score	Average	
Initial Activity			Implemented properly
1. Apperception	80		
2. Deliver objectives	100	90	
Main Activity			Implemented properly
1. Material orientation (guiding students to study learning material in the worksheet)	86		
2. Guiding students doing assignment in the worksheet	87		
3. Guiding students in discussion groups	78	83	
4. Guiding students writing and analyzing data in the worksheet	83		
5. Reflection of student's activity result worked in the worksheet	81		
Closing Activity			Implemented properly
1. Strengthening	90		
2. Giving further assignment	100	95	

Table 3 shows that the average score of SETS-based worksheet implementation is 89.33 and it belongs to high implementation category. It means that SETS-based worksheet is easy to implement in learning by teachers. In the initial activities the teachers deliver apperceptions to review materials that students have understood and these would be related to incoming materials to deliver. The teacher then delivers learning objectives. Initial activities in learning are very important to motivate students to be active in learning. In main activities the teachers is able to guide students in learning by using materials in SETS-based worksheet. Students are easy to understand materials delivered in the worksheet, because the materials are elaborated structurally following steps in SETS model. Students are active to do assignments in the worksheet. A good worksheet would ease students in learning. Active students are motivated to finish assignments given in the worksheet. This is in line with Assalma et al. (2013) suggesting that 'student's worksheet provides a fast and efficient way'. It indicates that using worksheet is very proper for fast and efficient learning, and it can help teachers and students in learning especially in integrated natural sciences learning materials.

SETS-based worksheet receives 83.29% students' positive responses. They are happy to learn by using SETS-based worksheet, because delivered materials are easy to understand and its assignments are not difficult to do. Learning materials in the worksheet are delivered form easy to difficult levels (inductive method). Problem solving examples are also given in the worksheet to help students doing problems. Findings in a study by Distrik et al. (2021) suggest that problem solving examples are able to guide students in implementing concepts for problem solving.

Effectiveness of SETS-based Worksheet in Improving Student's Critical Thinking Ability

SETS-based worksheet effectiveness is measured based on students' critical thinking ability test results. The results are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Students' critical thinking test results

No	Classroom	Type of Test		N-gain
		Pretest	Post-test	
1	Experiment	64.11	83.19	0.56
2	Control	56.50	67.17	0.27

Table 4 shows that n-gain of experiment classroom belongs to moderate category and n-gain of control classroom belongs to low category. Independent sample t-test result shows a significant difference of critical thinking abilities between experiment and control classrooms (sig. (2 tailed) < 0.05). This means that SETS-based worksheet is effective in improving student's critical thinking ability.

SETS-based worksheet is able to guide students in mastering sciences and technology. This is in line with a finding by Poedjiadi (2010) suggesting that learning with SETS approach is able to help students in mastering sciences and technologies, understanding how technologies are used and how science and technology developments influence environment and society. Hadiat (1984) also suggests that the objective of SETS learning is to enable students mastering scientific concepts to be used to answer environmental problems as impacts of technologies and other human activities. Learning by using worksheets enables students to do observation, record data, and use technology.

4. Conclusion

SETS-based worksheet has been validated with tests by experts and empirical tests. 1) Validity scores are 77 for content validity, 92 for construct validity, and 833.33 for language validity. Materials delivered in the SETS-based worksheet have been in accordance with curriculum, learning objectives, and logic. The language used in this worksheet is suitable with the student's age, not contradictory, and figures are in accordance with narrations. 2) Scores for SETS-based worksheet implementation is 89.33 and it belongs to high category of implementation. 83.29% students respond positively suggesting that this worksheet is easy to understand for learning. 3) This SETS-based worksheet is effective to improve critical thinking ability. It is indicated by n-gain difference between experiment and control classrooms. N-gain scores are 0.56 (moderate category) for experiment classroom and 0.27 (low category) for control classroom.

References

- Ali, H., & Muhlissarini. (2014). *Perencanaan dan Strategi Pembelajaran Matematika*. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Arends, R.I. (1997). *Classroom Instruction and Management*. McGraw Hill Companies. Inc. the United State of America
- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Sebuah Pendekatan Praktek*. Rineka Cipta.
- Assalma, N. E., Rahayu, E. S., & Iswari, R. S. (2013). Pengembangan Lembar Kerja Siswa Dengan Pendekatan Pembelajaran Berbasis Proyek (Pbp) Dan Berwawasan Salingtemas. *Journal of Biology Education*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.15294/jbe.v2i1.2613>
- Autieri, S. M., Amirshokoohi, & Kazempour. (2016). The Science-Technology Society Framework For Achieving Scientific Literacy: an overview of existing literature. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 41.
- Borg, W. ., & Gall, M. . (1983). *Educational Research: An Introduction*. Longman.
- BSNP. (2007). *Kurikulum Tingkat Satuan Pendidikan*. BSNP.
- Daud, A., & Suharyana, A. (2010). *Kajian Kritis Dalam Pembelajaran Matematika di SMP*. P4TK Matematika.
- Wayan Distrik, I., Imam Supardi, Z. A., Jatmiko, B., & Yuberti. (2021). The effects of multiple representations-based learning in improving concept understanding and problem-solving ability. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1796(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1796/1/012044>
- Hadiat, K. (1984). *Metodologi IPA*. Depdikbud.
- Komalasari, T. . (2020). *Proyeksi Bappenas: Penduduk Miskin Tahun 2020 Bertambah 2 Juta Orang*.
- Leicester, M., & Taylor, D. (2010). *Critical Thinking Across the Curriculum*. McGraw-HillOpen University Press.
- Poedjiadi, A. (2010). *Sains Teknologi Masyarakat*. PT. Remaja Rosdakarya Offset.
- Pramesthi, A. D. (2020). PENERAPAN LEMBAR KEGIATAN SISWA BERBASIS PENDEKATAN SALINGTEMAS PADA MATERI EKOSISTEM UNTUK MELATIHKAN KETERAMPILAN BERPIKIR KRITIS. *Bioedu*, 9(1).
- Prastowo, A. (2015). Perubahan Mindset dan Kesiapan Guru Sekolah Dasar dalam Persaingan Pendidikan di Era MEA). *In Seminar Nasional Profesionalisme Guru*, 627–628.
- Sugiyono. (2008). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan; Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Alfabeta CV.
- Sugiyono. (2013). *Cara Mudah Menyusun: Skripsi, Tesis, dan Disertasi*. CV Alfabeta.
- Sugiyono. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif, Kuantitatif, dan R & D*. Alfabeta.
- Suwarma, & Mayadiana, D. (2009). *Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Matematika*. Cakrawala Maha Karya.
- WaughDuron, L. (2006). Critical Thinking Framework For Any Discipline. *International Journal of Teaching Ad Learning in Higher Education*., 172.
- Wijaya, C. (2010). *Pendidikan Remedial*. Remaja Rosda Karya.